

E2.5: Intelligent 6G Platform Architecture v1.0

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4 List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ETL	extraction, transformation, and loading
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCM	Life-cycle Management
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
TOML	Tom's Obvious, Minimal Language
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
XAI	Explainable AI

5 Executive Summary

Deliverable E2.5 presents the culmination of efforts outlined in task A2.5 of the 6GENABLERS project (IA para 6G: Ultra Automatización y Optimización, reference number TSI-063000-2021-10). It synthesizes various technological enablers into an Intelligent 6G Platform Architecture. Indeed, the architecture capitalizes on Kubernetes clusters and namespaces, coupled with OpenTelemetry integration from OPTARE and OpenNebula's orchestrative capabilities. These components, combined with transparent MLOps and adherence to ETSI ZSM standards, yield a resilient and agile infrastructure, primed for deploying and managing the innovative holoportation service stack. Key features include a Telemetry Protocol utilizing HTTPS and JSON formats for standardized data exchange, alongside InfluxDB's advanced concurrency management, offering configurable write consistency, sharding for scalability, and query optimization. Additionally, the incorporation of FEAST as a Feature Store enhances data consistency, scalability, and intelligence within the platform. These advanced technologies unlock opportunities for real-time analytics, seamless machine learning integration, and intelligent decision-making.

6 Introduction

Among Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLC) services stands holoportation, a marvel of technology allowing for real-time, high-fidelity holographic communication. Yet, delivering such an experience demands the amalgamation of multiple technological enablers into a new 6G intelligent platform architecture. At its core, this architecture leverages Kubernetes clusters and namespaces to isolate the different components, seamlessly integrating OpenTelemetry from OPTARE and OpenNebula orchestrator with a transparent MLOps plane.

This commitment to transparency and adherence to ETSI ZSM standards not only ensures interoperability and compatibility but also instills a sense of trust and reliability in the system's operation. Central to the platform's functionality is its Telemetry which employs HTTPS and JSON formats for standardized data exchange. Complemented by InfluxDB's advanced concurrency management capabilities, including configurable write consistency, sharding for scalability, and query optimization, the platform stands ready to handle the demands of real-time data processing inherent in URLLC services such as holoportation.

Furthermore, the integration of FEAST as a Feature Store enhances data consistency, scalability, and intelligence within the platform, unlocking a plethora of opportunities for real-time analytics, seamless machine learning integration, and intelligent decision-making.

Finally, AI resource allocation models delivered by the MLOps pipeline enable the scaling of the holoportation stack in a closed-loop fashion.

7 Enablers

This section covers background information on the enablers of the designed 6G platform architecture.

7.1 Kubernetes Clusters and Namespaces

Kubernetes clusters and namespaces are important concepts to implement a 6G platform architecture.

Figure 1 K8s cluster and namespaces.

A Kubernetes cluster is a set of nodes (physical or virtual machines) that run containerized applications managed by Kubernetes. It comprises several components like the master node(s) and worker node(s). The master node controls the cluster and schedules workloads, while the worker nodes execute those workloads. In the context of a 6G platform architecture, Kubernetes clusters play a crucial role in providing the underlying infrastructure for deploying and managing various components of the platform. This includes compute resource allocation to different components of the 6G platform based on their requirements. It also defines how containers, pods, and services within Kubernetes communicate with each other. Kubernetes clusters enable high availability by automatically distributing workloads across multiple nodes and ensuring that services remain accessible even in the event of node failures. They also support horizontal scaling, allowing the platform to handle varying loads efficiently.

In Kubernetes, namespaces provide a way to partition cluster resources among multiple users or applications. They are virtual clusters within a physical Kubernetes cluster, allowing teams to create isolated environments with their own sets of resources. In the context of a 6G platform architecture, namespaces offer several benefits:

- **Isolation and security:** Different teams or components within the platform can operate in their own namespaces, ensuring isolation and security. This prevents interference or unauthorized access between different parts of the platform.
- **Resource management:** Namespaces allow for more granular resource allocation and management within the Kubernetes cluster. Each namespace can have its own resource quotas and limits, preventing one part of the platform from monopolizing resources and affecting others.

- Multi-tenancy: For a 6G platform serving multiple tenants or customers, namespaces enable multi-tenancy by providing segregated environments for each tenant while sharing the same underlying infrastructure.

The orchestrator makes use of Kubernetes Core API calls, which is one of the Northbound APIs provided by Kubernetes to programmatically manage Kubernetes resources such as namespaces, pods, deployments. For instance, it uses the `create_namespace` method of the `CoreV1Api` class to send a request to the Kubernetes API server for creating the namespace.

In summary, Kubernetes clusters provide the foundation for deploying and managing the various components of a 6G platform, while namespaces offer a way to organize and isolate these components within the cluster, ensuring efficient resource utilization, security, and scalability. Together, they form the backbone of a robust and scalable infrastructure for implementing advanced 6G services and applications.

7.2 Open Telemetry

OPTARE's OpenTelemetry platform plays a pivotal role in the architecture by providing a standardized approach for collecting telemetry data from distributed systems, allowing seamless integration and analysis of performance metrics across Edge and cloud environments. By adhering to TM Forum compliance standards, the architecture ensures interoperability and compatibility with industry best practices, facilitating seamless integration with existing systems and enabling efficient communication and data exchange between components. This adherence to standards promotes scalability, flexibility, and reliability, making it easier for organizations to deploy and manage complex Edge cloud architectures while maintaining alignment with industry norms and regulations.

Figure 2 Applications generate a multitude of telemetry data, including logs, traces, and metrics¹

¹ OPTARE, E2.4 Report on requirements for high-precision smart telemetry, 2023.

7.3 InfluxDB Time-Series Database

Choosing InfluxDB to enable time-series-oriented monitoring and statistical aggregation functions for 6G Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) offers distinct technical advantages. InfluxDB utilizes a highly efficient storage engine known as Time-Structured Merge (TSM), specifically optimized for time-series data. This architecture enables faster queries, crucial for handling the high-frequency data streams inherent in 6G networks. Additionally, InfluxDB's tag-based data model and native support for precision timestamps allow for precise data organization and efficient querying. When implementing statistical aggregation functions like percentile calculations, InfluxDB's built-in capabilities and indexing mechanisms enhance query performance, ensuring timely and accurate data analysis. Moreover, features such as continuous queries and retention policies streamline data management, facilitating both real-time monitoring and historical analysis. In summary, InfluxDB's tailored design for time-series data makes it a robust and efficient choice for the intricate requirements of 6G KPI monitoring and advanced statistical aggregation functions.

Figure 3 InfluxDB 3.0 Architecture²

7.4 Open-Source Orchestration

OpenNebula is an open-source cloud platform that offers advanced orchestration functionalities for virtualized infrastructures. Network Management: OpenNebula facilitates the creation and management of virtual networks, enabling users to define and configure network connectivity for their cloud infrastructure. It supports hybrid cloud deployments, allowing to seamlessly integrate on-premises infrastructure with public cloud services. OpenNebula also provides automation and orchestration capabilities for

² [InfluxDB 3.0: System Architecture | InfluxData](#)

managing complex workflows and orchestrating tasks across distributed computing resources. It supports multi-tenancy, enabling to isolate and manage multiple virtualized environments within a single OpenNebula deployment, which is needed to ensure that multiple AR pipelines can coexist in the system.

Additionally, OpenNebula is responsible for deploying and managing the virtualized AR pipelines in the selected Edge locations and takes on the responsibility of deploying any associated elements, including virtual networks, using its internal Software-Defined Networking (SDN) capabilities.

7.5 Transparent MLOps Pipeline

The architecture emphasized by 6GENABLERS-AI prioritizes the integration of MLOps and Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) within a transparent and dedicated network slice, thereby streamlining all AI Lifecycle Management (LCM) operations. This approach underscores the significance of transparency and accessibility in the MLOps plane, which features an innovative XAI closed loop, where an Explainer evaluates the model's confidence score and provides feedback to the optimizer, constraining the training process accordingly. This transparent feedback loop enhances the trustworthiness of the AI models and facilitates informed decision-making. This MLOps plane serves then the other network domains/slices by providing artifacts for enabling intelligent scaling of the holoportation stack at Edge. This modular design fosters scalability by eliminating the need for dedicated pipelines and enabling independent evolution of the MLOps layer alongside service layers. Furthermore, the philosophy of centralized training and decentralized execution, facilitated by a cloud-based pipeline and edge resource allocation model, underscores the importance of efficient resource utilization and distributed processing capabilities.

8 Intelligent 6G Platform Architecture

8.1 Architecture Description

Figure 4 6G intelligent architecture.

In the designed architecture shown in Figure 4, the integration of Kubernetes clusters and namespaces is paramount for facilitating efficient and scalable deployment of applications and services. At the heart of this architecture lies the need for robust management of resources and isolation of functionalities to ensure seamless operation. The Edge cluster, responsible for executing the holoportation application stack and core network functions, relies on OpenNebula for orchestrating containerized workloads across distributed nodes. It enables dynamic scaling and load balancing, critical for handling variable demand and ensuring optimal performance of the Edge applications.

Moreover, the segmentation of the cloud environment into namespaces enhances organizational control and resource allocation. In this scenario, the cloud environment is partitioned into two distinct namespaces: one dedicated to MLOps pipeline operations and the other designated for telemetry and InfluxDB data aggregation. This separation of concerns not only simplifies management but also ensures scalability and fault isolation. By isolating the MLOps pipeline within its own namespace, resources can be allocated and scaled independently based on the requirements of machine learning workflows, without impacting the performance of other components.

Inter-namespace communication is facilitated through Kubernetes APIs and service discovery mechanisms. For instance, the MLOps pipeline namespace can utilize Kubernetes Services to expose endpoints that allow the exchange of data and information with the telemetry namespace. Additionally, Kubernetes supports network policies to control traffic flow between namespaces, ensuring secure and efficient communication while maintaining isolation.

The dedicated namespace for MLOps operations offers several advantages. Firstly, it streamlines the deployment and management of machine learning workflows, providing a focused environment for model training, testing, and inference. Secondly, by decoupling MLOps from other components, such as the Edge cluster and telemetry data aggregation, scalability can be achieved without interference or contention for resources. This isolation guarantees the reliability and performance of critical machine learning tasks, contributing to the overall resilience of the Edge cloud architecture.

Moreover, the trained resource allocation model within the MLOps namespace plays a pivotal role in enhancing Edge functionality. This model, serving as a guide for resource distribution and optimization, is leveraged by the Edge cluster to dynamically scale the holoportation application stack based on real-time demand and performance metrics. By integrating the insights gleaned from MLOps operations, the Edge cluster can adapt and respond to changing conditions, ensuring efficient utilization of resources while maintaining high-quality service delivery.

8.2 Interfaces, Protocols and Features

8.2.1 Telemetry Protocol and Format

The telemetry protocol and format utilized between metric exporters and collectors typically rely on JSON for its lightweight nature, facilitating real-time processing and communication. JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) offers a streamlined format for exchanging raw telemetry data due to its simplicity and readability. Leveraging HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) as the communication protocol ensures secure transmission of data between exporters and collectors, safeguarding against potential security threats. HTTPS encrypts data during transit, mitigating the risk of eavesdropping and tampering. Additionally, HTTPS operates over standard port 443, ensuring compatibility with existing network infrastructure and firewalls. This combination of JSON format and HTTPS protocol fosters efficient and secure exchange of telemetry data, enabling seamless integration and analysis within monitoring systems.

```
{
  "timestamp": "2024-02-07T08:00:00Z",
  "server": "cloud-server-1",
  "metrics": {
    "cpu_usage_percent": 25.6,
    "memory_usage_percent": 65.2,
    "disk_usage_percent": 42.3,
    "network_traffic_in_bytes": {
      "received": 102400,
      "transmitted": 204800
    },
    "temperature_celsius": 37.8
  },
  "tags": {
    "region": "us-west-1",
    "environment": "production"
  }
}
```

Figure 5 Telemetry JSON format example.

8.2.2 InfluxDB Concurrency Management

InfluxDB's concurrency management is facilitated through its configuration file, `influxdb.conf`, written in TOML format, allowing to define various parameters and settings. Features such as configurable write consistency, sharding for scalability, and query optimization can be activated and tailored within this file. Write consistency levels can be adjusted to balance data integrity and performance, while sharding capabilities distribute data across nodes for efficient resource utilization. Horizontal scaling further enhances scalability, enabling seamless expansion as data demands increase. Query optimization mechanisms minimize latency and improve system responsiveness. By configuring settings within `influxdb.conf`, users can effectively manage concurrent data operations according to their specific workload requirements.

```

logging-enabled = true

[data]
dir = "/var/lib/influxdb/data"
wal-dir = "/var/lib/influxdb/wal"
query-log-enabled = true
retention-autocreate = true
retention-check-enabled = true

[http]
bind-address = ":8086"
auth-enabled = true
log-enabled = true

[logging]
format = "auto"
level = "info"
suppress-logo = false

[data]
index-version = "ts1l" # Configures the index version for the database

[data]
trace-logging-enabled = false # Disable trace logging

[data]
max-values-per-tag = 0 # Unlimited number of tag values

[data]
max-series-per-database = 0 # Unlimited number of series per database

[coordinator]
write-timeout = "10s" # Sets the maximum time a write request is held

[retention]
enabled = true # Enables retention policy enforcement

[shard-precreation]
enabled = true # Enables shard pre-creation service

[monitor]
store-enabled = true # Enables monitoring the storage engine

```

Figure 6 InfluxDB configuration file example.

8.2.3 FEAST

FEAST (Feature Store) serves as a centralized repository for storing and managing features, providing a unified source of truth for feature data across various applications and services. By leveraging FEAST, we can ensure that feature data used for machine learning models, analytics, and other data-driven processes remains consistent and up-

to-date. With InfluxDB as our time-series database, we can seamlessly ingest and store time-stamped feature data, enriching our datasets with contextual information vital for analysis and decision-making. Additionally, integrating FEAST with OPTARE enables efficient feature extraction, transformation, and loading (ETL) processes, streamlining the flow of feature data from diverse sources into our analytical pipelines. This integration not only enhances data consistency but also empowers us to derive deeper insights and drive more accurate predictions.

Figure 7 Feature store³

8.3 Workflow

The above intelligent platform architecture can be used as follows:

- **Data Ingestion and Telemetry Collection:** Data sources at the edge and cloud domains continuously generate telemetry data which is collected by exporters and sent to OPTARE's open telemetry system in the cloud for aggregation and analysis. This entails continuous monitoring of the clusters/namespaces for performance, resource utilization, and potential issues, as well as raising automated alerts and notifications for proactive maintenance and troubleshooting.
- **Telemetry Data Aggregation:** Telemetry data is aggregated using InfluxDB within the telemetry namespace. Aggregated data is stored and made available for consumption by other components.
- **Transparent MLOps Pipeline:** MLOps pipeline continuously monitors model performance and trigger re-training/updates based on new data received from InfluxDB.
- **Trustworthy Resource Allocation Model Training:** Using historical telemetry data and performance metrics, a resource allocation model is trained within the MLOps namespace. The model learns to predict resource requirements for scaling the holoportation application based on demand patterns.
- **Model Serving and Integration with Edge Cluster:** The trained resource allocation model is served to the Edge cluster. Based on the model's predictions,

³ [Feast: Feature Store for Machine Learning](#)

the Edge cluster dynamically adjusts the number of replicas and resources allocated to the holoportation application stack.

- **Holoportation Application Execution on Edge Cluster:** Holoportation application stack and core network functionalities are deployed and executed on the Edge cluster.
- **Orchestration:** OpenNebula’s orchestrator orchestrates the various containerized workloads in the Edge-Cloud continuum, ensuring efficient resource utilization and dynamic scaling based on demand.

8.4 Mapping to Testbed

Mapping the described architecture to a testbed with two servers, namely "Higher End" and "Edge," both managed by a Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) and hosting Kubernetes clusters orchestrated by OpenNebula:

Table 1 Testbed components

Server	Configuration	Role	Kubernetes Cluster	Namespace Configuration	Functionality
Higher End Server (Cloud):	64 cores, 512 GB RAM, 2048 GB disk, GPU performance similar or superior to NVIDIA Tesla T4 or NVIDIA Tesla V100.	Represents the higher-end cloud infrastructure.	Hosts a Kubernetes cluster managed by OpenNebula.	-MLOps Namespace: Dedicated namespace for machine learning operations, including model training, inference, and resource allocation. -Telemetry Namespace: Namespace for OPTARE telemetry data aggregation and analysis.	-Aggregates telemetry data from the Edge server. -Hosts the MLOps pipeline for training and deploying machine learning models.
Edge Server	48 cores, 128 GB RAM, 2048 GB disk	Represents the edge computing infrastructure	Hosts a Kubernetes cluster managed by OpenNebula.	Default namespace	-Executes the holoportation application stack and core network functionalities. -Request the resource allocation model re-training from the MLOps pipeline hosted on the Higher End server. -Dynamically scales the holoportation application stack based on recommendations from the resource allocation model. -Sends telemetry data to the Higher End server for aggregation and analysis.

By utilizing this testbed configuration, 6GENABLERS-AI can validate and test the described architecture in a controlled environment. The distributed nature of the infrastructure allows for geographic distribution of workloads related to artificial intelligence, ensuring efficient resource utilization and scalability across cloud and edge environments.

8.5 ETSI ZSM Compliance

Figure 8 ETSI closed-loop management.

The architecture aligns with the principles and requirements outlined by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) framework in terms of:

- **Service Orchestration and Automation:**
 - The architecture leverages Kubernetes clusters managed by OpenNebula, which act as the underlying infrastructure for service orchestration.
 - OpenNebula orchestrates the deployment and management of containers and virtualized resources across the Edge and Higher End servers.

ETSI ZSM emphasizes the automation of service lifecycle management, and this architecture achieves it by dynamically scaling applications, optimizing resource allocation, and managing workloads seamlessly.

- **Closed-Loop Automation:**
 - Telemetry data from the Edge server is continuously collected and sent to the Higher End server for aggregation and analysis within the orchestration namespace.
 - Transparent MLOps pipeline namespace leverages this telemetry data to train and refine resource allocation models, which are then served to the Edge domain to perform scaling recommendations based on real-time data and demand patterns.
 - This closed-loop automation process ensures that the architecture can adapt to changing conditions and optimize resource utilization without manual intervention.

ETSI ZSM emphasizes closed-loop automation to achieve self-optimization, self-configuration, and self-healing capabilities, which this architecture demonstrates by dynamically scaling and optimizing Edge applications based on telemetry data and AI models.

- **End-to-End Service Management:**
 - The architecture covers the entire service lifecycle, from data ingestion and telemetry collection to machine learning model training and application scaling.
 - By integrating Edge and cloud resources, it enables end-to-end service management and optimization, ensuring efficient and reliable operation of Edge applications.

ETSI ZSM promotes end-to-end service management to achieve service agility, flexibility, and optimization, all of which are supported by this architecture through its seamless integration of Edge and cloud environments.

In summary, the architecture aligns with ETSI ZSM principles by enabling service orchestration, closed-loop automation, and end-to-end service management. It demonstrates how Edge computing can be integrated with cloud resources to achieve efficient, automated, and optimized service delivery in compliance with ETSI standards.

9 Conclusion

Deliverable E2.5 of the 6GENABLERS-AI project has presented an Intelligent 6G Platform Architecture forged through the synthesis of various technological enablers. This architecture leverages Kubernetes clusters and namespaces, in conjunction with OpenTelemetry integration from OPTARE, the orchestrative capabilities of OpenNebula and a transparent MLOps plane in a closed-loop design that adheres to ETSI ZSM, ensuring a resilient and agile infrastructure suited for deploying and managing holoportation services.

Key features of this architecture include an OpenTelemetry protocol employing HTTPS and JSON formats for standardized data exchange, supported by InfluxDB's advanced concurrency management capabilities. Additionally, the incorporation of FEAST as a Feature Store enhances data consistency, scalability, and intelligence within the platform. The centralized training decentralized execution of the AI resource allocation model allow a fast provisioning/scaling of the edge holoportation service.

These technological advancements pave the way for real-time analytics, seamless machine learning integration, and intelligent decision-making, highlighting the platform's potential in advancing telecommunications capabilities.